

EFFECT OF MATRIX YIELDING ON THE STRESS TRANSFER IN FIBRE FRAGMENTATION TEST

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ABSTRACT

The micromechanics of stress transfer is analyzed in the fibre fragmentation test of composites with yielded matrix at the interface region. The criteria for interfacial matrix yielding and fibre fracture are derived. Depending on the relative magnitudes of the matrix shear yield strength and fibre tensile strength for given elastic constants and geometric factors, the conditions required to satisfy the interfaces with full bonding and partial yielding are evaluated. The mean fibre fragment length is predicted for a model composite of carbon fibre-polyetheretherketone (PEEK) matrix.

INTRODUCTION

The study of the fibre-matrix interfacial phenomena in fibre composites has attracted a significant volume of research as a result of the important role of the interface in constituting the mechanical performance and structural integrity of the composites [1,2]. The primary functions of the interface are to allow efficient stress transfer between the composite constituents and to protect the reinforcing fibres in adverse environment. Following the previous theoretical study on interface debonding and fibre pull-out processes in fibre pull-out test of single [3] and multiple fibre composites [4], the micromechanics of elastic stress transfer is analyzed in the fibre fragmentation test geometry [5]. Depending on the interface properties and fibre tensile strength for given elastic constants of the composite constituents, three distinct interface situations are identified which include full bonding, partial debonding and full frictional bonding. The conditions required to satisfy each interface are also identified. The effects of interaction between the neighbouring fibres on the two opposing failure mechanisms, namely fibre fracture and interface debonding, are evaluated using the three cylinder composite model [6].

In addition to interface debonding, there is substantial amount of evidence available that in many polymer matrix composites the matrix material immediately adjacent to the fibre surface yields and plastically deforms [7]. The maximum interface shear stresses determined from the laser Raman spectroscopy study [8,9] are found to correlate well with the shear yield strength of the matrix materials of different chemical structures. This implies that shear yielding has taken place in the matrix material at the interface near the fibre ends. The thin layers and particles of resins adhering to the fibre surface [10,11] further support the above failure

mechanisms. In metal matrix composites, nucleation of cavities often takes place near the stiff fibres. All these plastic deformation is promoted by the high level of triaxial constraint and the enhanced degree of non-elastic deformation between the reinforcing fibres as a result of localisation of the applied stress.

As a continuation of the previous study, the theoretical analysis of matrix yielding at the interface region is further extended for the fibre fragmentation test geometry. The criteria for interfacial matrix yielding and fibre fracture are evaluated, and the conditions to satisfy these fracture modes are identified.

Figure 1. A schematic drawing of the partially yielded matrix at the interface region in the fibre fragmentation model.

MICROMECHANICS ANALYSIS

SOLUTIONS FOR THE STRESS FIELDS

The geometry of the model and the governing conditions employed in the present analysis are basically the same as those used in our previous work [5]. The shear-lag model in cylindrical coordinate (r, θ, z) shown in Figure 1 is symmetric about the fibre axis $r = 0$ and the mid-plane at $z = 0$. A single fibre of total length $2L$ with a yielded interface length l_y at its both ends is embedded at the centre of a cylindrical shell of matrix material. When a tensile stress, σ , is applied to the matrix at the remote ends, stress is transferred to the fibre across the interface. The solutions for the fibre axial stress (FAS) and interface shear stress (ISS) in the bonded region $(-L-l_y) \leq z \leq (L-l_y)$ are derived [5]:

$$\sigma_f^z(z) = \frac{1+\gamma}{\alpha+\gamma} \left[1 - \frac{\cosh(\beta_2 z)}{\cosh[\beta_2(L-l_y)]} \right] \sigma + \frac{\cosh(\beta_2 z)}{\cosh[\beta_2(L-l_y)]} \sigma_{\theta_y} \quad (1)$$

$$\tau_i(z) = \frac{\alpha\beta_2}{2} \left[\frac{1+\gamma}{\alpha+\gamma} \sigma - \sigma_{\theta_y} \right] \frac{\sinh(\beta_2 z)}{\cosh[\beta_2(L-l_y)]} \quad (2)$$

where

$$\beta_2^2 = \frac{a^2 \left[\left(\frac{b}{a}\right)^2 - 1 \right] (1 + \frac{\alpha}{\gamma})}{(1+\gamma) \left\{ \left(\frac{b}{a}\right)^4 \ln\left(\frac{b}{a}\right) - \frac{1}{2\gamma^2} - \frac{1}{4\gamma} \left[\left(\frac{b}{a}\right)^2 + 1 \right] \right\}} \quad (3)$$

The Young's modulus ratio of the matrix to the fibre $\alpha = E_m/E_f$, and the volume ratio of the fibre to the matrix $\gamma = a^2/(b^2 - a^2)$. σ_{fy} is the fibre axial stress (FAS) at the boundary between the bonded and yielded interface regions. If the interface is fully bonded, the above equations are still valid except for $\sigma_{fy} = 0$ and $\ell_y = 0$.

At this stage we assume a shear strength criterion in that the matrix material yields at the interface region when the interface shear stress reaches the matrix shear yield strength, τ_{my} , which is a material constant. It is also assumed that the apparent interface bond strength is significantly greater than the matrix shear yield strength so that matrix yielding occurs in preference to debonding at the interface region. Therefore, the corresponding solutions for the stress components in the yielded regions ($-L \leq z \leq -(L-\ell_y)$) and $(L-\ell_y) \leq z \leq L$) are obtained:

$$\sigma_f^z(z) = \frac{2}{a} \tau_{my} (L - z) \tag{4}$$

$$\tau_i(z) = \tau_{my} \tag{5}$$

The fibre axial stress (FAS) at the boundary between the bonded and yielded region, σ_{fy} , is determined from Eq. (4) for $z = (L-\ell_y)$:

$$\sigma_{fy} = \frac{2\ell_y}{a} \tau_{my} \tag{6}$$

CRITERIA FOR INTERFACE YIELDING AND FIBRE FRAGMENTATION

Based on the solutions for the stress components in the composite constituents one can derive the relevant criteria for matrix yielding at the interface and fibre fragmentation. The conditions required to satisfy the interface states with full bonding and partial matrix yielding are also identified in terms of the relationship between the applied stress and the properties of the constituents. Further, the fibre fragmentation criterion is applied to derive the mean fibre fragment length, $2L$, as a function of the applied stress for each interface state. Thus, the external stress applied to the matrix, $\sigma = \sigma_{oy}$, for matrix yielding at the interface is obtained from Eq. (2) for $\tau_i(L-\ell_y) = \tau_{my}$:

$$\sigma_{oy} = \frac{\alpha + \gamma}{1 + \gamma} \frac{2\tau_{my}}{a} \left[\ell_y + \frac{1}{\beta_2} \coth[\beta_2(L-\ell_y)] \right] \tag{7}$$

The fibre fragmentation criterion is chosen here such that when the applied stress is high enough to cause the maximum FAS to reach the local tensile strength, the fibre fractures. A fibre tensile strength model similar to that employed before [5,6] is used to predict the average strength of the fibre of length $2L$, $\sigma_{TS}(2L)$, based on the Weibull probability of failure:

$$\sigma_{TS}(2L) = (\sigma_u)^{-\frac{1}{m}} \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{m}\right) \left(\frac{L_g}{L}\right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \tag{8}$$

where L_g is the fibre gauge length. m and σ_u are the Weibull modulus and the scale factor, and Γ the gamma function. Assuming the fibre always fractures at the centre where the FAS is maximum, the external stress required for fibre fragmentation, $\sigma = \sigma_{of}$, is derived:

$$\sigma_{of} = \frac{\alpha + \gamma}{1 + \gamma} \frac{\sigma_{TS} \cosh[\beta_2(L - \ell_y)] - \frac{2\ell_y}{a} \tau_{my}}{\cosh[\beta_2(L - \ell_y)] - 1} \quad (9)$$

FULLY BONDED INTERFACE

The criteria for initial matrix yielding and for fibre fracture can be obtained by replacing $\ell_y = 0$ in Eqs. (7) and (9), respectively. For the interface to remain fully bonded during the fibre fragmentation process, the maximum ISS obtained at the fibre ends in Eq. (2) with $\ell_y = 0$ must always be smaller than the critical value, τ_{my} :

$$\tau_{my} > \frac{a\beta_2}{2} \frac{\sigma_{TS} \sinh(\beta_2 L)}{\cosh(\beta_2 L) - 1} \quad (10)$$

For the fully bonded interface, the average fibre fragment length, $2L$, is given [5]:

$$2L = \frac{2}{\beta_2} \cosh^{-1} \left[\frac{\sigma_{of}}{\sigma_{of} - \frac{\alpha + \gamma}{1 + \gamma} \sigma_{TS}} \right] \quad (11)$$

Figure 2. (a) Normalised fibre axial stress and (b) normalised interface shear stress along the fibre axis for matrix Young's moduli, $E_m = 1.5, 3.8$ and 6.0 MPa.

PARTIALLY YIELDED INTERFACE

Once the interface is partially yielded at a length ℓ_y , whether interfacial yielding continues or fibre fractures depends on the relative magnitudes of the stresses required for matrix yielding, σ_{oy} , and for fibre fragmentation, σ_{of} . If σ_{oy} is smaller than σ_{of} , interfacial matrix yielding continues in preference to fibre fracture; and conversely, if σ_{oy} is greater than σ_{of} , then vice versa. Thus, the condition for continuation of matrix yielding is given:

$$\tau_{my} < \frac{\sigma_{TS}}{\left(\frac{2}{a}\right) \left[\ell_y + \frac{1}{\beta_2} \frac{\cosh[\beta_2(L-\ell_y)] - 1}{\sinh[\beta_2(L-\ell_y)]} \right]} \quad (12)$$

Once the partial yielding condition is satisfied, the mean fibre fragment length, $2L$, which is the sum of the bonded and yielded interface lengths, can be determined from Eqs. (7) and (9):

$$2L = 2\ell_y + \frac{2}{\beta_2} \cosh^{-1} \left[\frac{\sigma_{of} - \frac{\alpha+\gamma}{1+\gamma} \frac{2\ell_y}{a} \tau_{my}}{\sigma_{of} - \frac{\alpha+\gamma}{1+\gamma} \sigma_{TS}} \right] \quad (13)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Specific results are calculated using the solutions generated previously for the model composite containing carbon fibre and polyetheretherketone (PEEK) matrix. The mechanical properties used for calculations are $E_f = 230$ GPa, $E_m = 3.8$ GPa, $\nu_f = 0.2$, $\nu_m = 0.4$, $\tau_{my} = 46$ MPa, unless otherwise specified. The Weibull statistics for the fibre tensile strength are $2L_g = 12$ mm, $\sigma_{TS}(2L_g) = 2.35$ GPa, $m = 3.8$, $\sigma_u = 5.0$ [5].

The FAS and ISS distributions normalised with applied stress are plotted as a function of normalised axial distance in Figure 2. The difference in matrix Young's modulus, E_m , is reflected by the variation in the maximum values obtained in the centre and at the ends of the fibre for the FAS and ISS, respectively, while the general trends are essentially identical for different E_m values.

Figure 3 Plots of applied stress, σ , as a function of fibre length, $2L$, for three different matrix shear yield strength, $\tau_{my} = 30, 46$ and 60 MPa.

The curves plotted based on Eqs. (7) and (9) with $\ell_y = 0$ in Figure 3 display the critical combinations of the applied stress and the fibre length required for initial matrix shear yielding and fibre fracture to take place. The areas above and below the curves for σ_{oy} represent, respectively, full bonding and matrix yielding at the interface region. In the same manner, the curve for σ_{of} represent the critical applied stress required for fibre fragmentation before matrix yielding can occur. It is noted that the σ_{oy} curves are constant independent of fibre length except for very short length, while the σ_{of} curve decreases continuously as fibre length increases.

If the fibre is sufficiently long, it fractures without interfacial matrix yielding because $\sigma_{oy} > \sigma_{of}$. Fibre fragmentation continues until the fibre length becomes a characteristic value, $(2L)_{my}$, below which the matrix material begins to yield at the interface region. $(2L)_{my}$ decreases with increasing matrix shear yield strength, τ_{my} . $(2L)_{my} = 24.3$ and 8.8 mm are obtained for $\tau_{my} = 46$ and 60 MPa, respectively. This observation has a significant implication in practical composites containing aligned discontinuous fibres in that the matrix shear yield strength, τ_{my} , and initial fibre length, $2L$, can be tailored to provide optimum mechanical performance depending on the failure modes which are least desired to occur. With regard to the effect of matrix shear yield strength, τ_{my} , the plateau values of σ_{oy} increases with increasing τ_{my} , whereas the σ_{of} curve is completely insensitive to the variation of τ_{my} . The constant $\sigma_{oy} = 21.0, 32.2$ and 42.0 MPa are obtained respectively for $\tau_{my} = 30, 46$ and 60 MPa.

Figure 4. Distributions of (a) fibre axial stress and (b) interface shear stress along the fibre axis, z/a , at a given applied stress $\sigma = 62.2$ MPa for three different τ_{my} values of 30 MPa, 46 and 60 MPa.

The FAS and ISS distributions for the partially yielded interface are shown in Figure 4. The matrix yield lengths are different for different τ_{my} values when the applied stress is kept constant $\sigma = 62.2$ MPa for a given fibre length $2L = 2$ mm. Both the FAS and ISS are almost identical for these τ_{my} values, except near the fibre ends. A higher τ_{my} results in a higher stress distributions at the boundary between the bonded and yielded regions for both FAS and ISS. The constant ISS values at the yielded interface region are identical to the τ_{my} values used for the calculation, directly reflecting the boundary conditions.

The applied stresses σ_{oy} and σ_{of} are plotted as a function of yield length, ℓ_y/a , in Figure 5. It is shown that for a fibre length $2L = 2$ mm interfacial matrix yielding initiates at a low applied stress, and it grows until the applied stress reaches σ_{of} , depending on the matrix shear

yield strength, τ_{my} . The maximum yielded interface length, $(2\ell_y)_m = 0.125, 0.059$ and 0.031 mm are determined for $\tau_{my} = 30, 46$ and 60 MPa. The σ_{oy} value for a given yield length increases as τ_{my} increases, which agrees with the observation from Figure 3. In contrast, the σ_{of} value is shown almost constant independent of matrix shear yield strength for a given fibre length. The decaying portions of the σ_{of} curves at a long yield length have no practical significance since interfacial matrix yielding cannot continue beyond the maximum value $(2\ell_y)_m$.

Figure 5. Plots of applied stress required for matrix yielding, σ_{oy} , and for fibre fragmentation, σ_{of} , as a function of normalised yield length, ℓ_y/a , for different matrix shear yield strength, $\tau_{my} = 30, 46$ and 60 MPa for $2L = 2$ mm.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

A theoretical analysis of interfacial matrix yielding and fibre fracture is developed in the single fibre microcomposite on the basis of the shear strength criterion and the average fibre tensile strength model. Stress fields are characterised in the fibre and at the fibre-matrix interface for both the fully bonded and partially yielded interfaces. In a parametric study on a typical carbon fibre-polyetheretherketone matrix composite, it is identified that there is a characteristic fibre length above which the fibre fractures without matrix shear yielding at the interface region. For partially yielded interface, whether matrix yielding continues or fibre fragmentation occurs depends strictly on the relative magnitudes of the applied stresses required for these two opposing failure processes. These applied stresses are governed by the two strength properties of the composite constituents: namely matrix shear yield strength and fibre tensile strength, for given elastic constants of the fibre and matrix and geometric factors of the model.

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